

Influence of Instructional Materials on Teaching and Learning Technical and Vocational Courses in Technical Colleges in Katsina State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the role of instructional materials in improving teaching and learning outcomes in Technical Colleges in Katsina State, Nigeria, with a focus on vocational and technical education. The effective integration of instructional materials is essential for enhancing educational quality and ensuring students acquire requisite skills for employment. Using a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from 60 respondents, including administrators, trade teachers, and workshop attendants. The study found that instructional materials are generally adequate and highly utilized, though ICT facilities are only moderately accessible. Results from ANOVA tests indicated no significant difference in the perceptions of students, teachers, and technicians regarding the adequacy, use, and accessibility of these materials. The study recommends that authorities improve access to modern digital tools and provide continuous training for educators to facilitate practical skill development.

Keywords: Influence, Instructional materials, Teaching & Learning, Technical, Vocational

INTRODUCTION

The influence of instructional materials on teaching and learning of technical courses in technical colleges has been noted in promoting students' academic performance, teaching and learning in educational development. Bassey (2002) described instructional materials media as system component that may be used as part of instructional process which are used to disseminate informative message and ideas or which make possible communication in the teaching-learning process. Experience over the years has shown that teachers have been depending on excessive use of words to express, convey ideas or facts in the teaching-learning process.

According to Bassey (2002), graphics including charts, posters, sketches, cartoons, graphs and drawings. Graphics communicate facts and ideas clearly through combination of drawings, words and pictures. The use of graphics in teaching creates definitiveness to the materials being studied. They help to visualize the whole concepts learned and their relationships with one another.

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During this process instructional material otherwise known as teaching aids meant to make instruction more meaningful, clear and much more interesting to students is brought in display. It is believed that if adequate instructional materials are made available to school and are used appropriately in teaching-learning process, a better performance could be achieved. Hence, the motivation of this study which seeks to find out the influence of instructional materials on academic performance of technical and vocational courses. Teachers who take time to provide instructional materials and option that take into consideration or account the different ways students receive and express knowledge are more likely to see their students' success. Science classroom should provide a variety of audio, visual and print input methods depending on students need, allow students the flexibility to communicate their true learning. Taylor, Scotter and Coulson (2007)

The teaching of technical and vocational courses in Nigerian technical colleges needs to be properly handled. Creativity contributes to the nation's economic development, hence, the need to be taught thoroughly if it is to meet the educational and economic development. Technical and vocational courses are the subjects in technical colleges, it cannot be taught effectively without the use of appropriate instructional materials (Ajayi, 1988). Learning by doing was emphasized in the curriculum so that the students should be able to understand the technical and vocational courses and learn to be creative.

In the Nigerian education system, technical colleges offer technical and vocational education programme for the purpose of producing middle level skilled manpower required for the nation's economic and technological development (Federal Republic of Nigeria [FRN], 2012). National Technical Certificate (NTC) is awarded by the National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) to students who have completed their post primary education at Technical Colleges (NABTEB, 2012).

The ultimate goal of vocational technical education and training is for the acquisition of knowledge, attitude and practical skills relating to occupations in various sectors for sustainable development and social life (FGN, 2014). The training of Vocational Technical Education for students is based on the production of goods and services that are not only relevant to themselves but to the society in general. Udoutin (2001) stated that the acquisition of life-long skills calls for effective and efficient teaching strategies, appropriate evaluation methods and utilization of standard teaching materials, tools, machines, and equipment to ensure the production of desired graduate with practical skills. Other requirements include training manuals and availability of qualified teachers with experiences which are in high demand in the labour market, but could be suitably motivated for part time teaching in Technical Colleges (Johnson & Adams, 2004).

Hence for effective and positive creative thinking to be done by students in technical colleges, there is supposed to be teaching aids that these students will accept and learn faster with.

The teacher alone cannot provide all the needed condition for effective teaching and learning process, other supporting materials should be provided. The students learn better when most of the senses are appealed to the instruction and use of instructional materials in creativity science education has added a new dimension in the positive promotion of the teaching and learning process. It provides the much need

sensory experiences needed by the learners for an effective and meaningful behavioural change, it has been a matter of great concern for quite some time that the performance of students in this subject has been persistently below our expectations, and what has been even more worrying is the poor understanding level of the subject. In this vein therefore, it would be meaningful to innovate newer strategies leading to the better achievement and understanding of the subject (Ibok, 2015).

Statement of Problem

The Nigerian education system faces a disturbing trend of poor academic performance in technical courses, reflected in both internal and external examinations. This decline is largely attributed to a reliance on verbal and theoretical teaching methods rather than practical application. Many students perceive technical concepts as abstract and lose interest because essential resources such as computers, projectors, and workshop equipment are either unavailable or underutilized.

As noted by Afolabi (2009), students frequently fail examinations due to improper teaching methods and a lack of essential instructional aids. Experience shows that spoken words alone are inefficient for producing desired learning outcomes in skill-based subjects. When teachers fail to improvise or provide relevant materials, students struggle to comprehend complex topics. This study, therefore, investigates how the use of instructional materials can bridge the gap between theory and practice and ultimately enhance the academic achievement of technical college students.

Objective of the Study

The main aim of the study is to critically analyse the impact of instructional materials in teaching and learning of technical courses in technical colleges in Katsina. The study tends to find out the following:

1. To determine the Instructional materials for effective teaching and learning technical courses in Katsina state.
2. To identify the Instructional materials as essential and significant tool for teaching and learning technical courses in Katsina state.
3. To determine the accessibility of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning technical courses in Katsina state.

Research Questions

In the field of technical courses, it has been observed that the use of instructional materials plays a major role to the teaching and learning of technical courses. Based on the above observation, the researcher generated the following questions to guide the study:

1. What is the adequacy of Instructional materials for effective teaching and learning technical courses in Katsina state?
2. What is the level of use of the Instructional materials as essential and significant tool for teaching and learning technical courses in Katsina state?
3. What is the Accessibility of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning technical courses in Katsina state?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses are formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Students, Technicians and BBC Teachers, on the adequacy of Instructional materials for effective teaching and learning in technical colleges in Katsina state.

HO₂. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Students, Technicians and BBC Teachers, on the use of Instructional Materials as Essential and Significant Tool in technical colleges in Katsina state

HO₃. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Students, Technicians and BBC Teachers, on the Accessibility of instructional materials for Effective Teaching and Learning in technical colleges in Katsina State.

Theoretical Foundations of Instructional Materials

The theoretical foundation of this study is anchored on an integrated perspective of cognitive and social learning processes. By synthesizing the Cognitive Theory of Instruction, Direct Instruction Theory,

Accountability Theory, and Vygotsky's Socio-Cultural Theory, the study establishes that technical skill acquisition is not an accidental occurrence. Instead, it is a structured process where instructional materials serve as essential mediators that simplify complex data, model professional behavior, and bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical competence.

1. Cognitive Theory of Instruction (Information Processing)

This theory views learning as an internal process of encoding and storing information. It suggests that instructional materials such as charts and models help students process complex data by transforming abstract concepts into logical, concrete experiences. By aligning teaching resources with the brain's cognitive limits, educators can facilitate better retention and the development of higher-order problem-solving skills in technical subjects (Evertson, 1980).

2. Direct Instruction Theory (Explicit Instruction)

Direct Instruction emphasizes systematic, teacher-led modeling and guided practice. It posits that technical skills are best acquired when teachers use real objects, machines, and visual aids to provide clear demonstrations and immediate feedback. This framework supports the idea that thinking skills are not innate but must be deliberately taught through structured interaction with relevant instructional tools.

3. Accountability Theory of Instruction

Proposed by Doyle (1983), this theory focuses on how instructional tasks and classroom expectations drive student behavior. It suggests that students engage more deeply when tasks are clearly defined by "instructional signals." In technical colleges, the presence and use of specific instructional materials serve as these cues, guiding student attention and providing clear benchmarks for success during practical lessons.

4. Socio-Cultural Theory of Learning (Vygotsky)

Lev Vygotsky's theory posits that cognitive development is driven by social interaction and the use of "cultural tools," such as instructional materials. In technical education, resources like machines, tools, and diagrams serve as mediating instruments that enhance problem-solving and critical thinking. These materials are essential for supporting learners within their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), effectively bridging the gap between a student's independent ability and their potential achievement under guided instruction.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

This section reviews empirical studies related to the influence of instructional materials on teaching and learning, particularly in technical and vocational education. The review is organized to reflect the key variables of the study and the theoretical foundations underpinning it.

Empirical Studies on Instructional Materials and Teaching–Learning Process

Several empirical studies have established a strong relationship between instructional materials and effective teaching and learning. Afolabi (2009) investigated the effect of instructional materials on students' academic achievement and found that students taught with appropriate instructional materials performed significantly better than those taught without such materials. The study concluded that instructional materials enhance comprehension and retention of knowledge.

Similarly, Yusuf and Afolabi (2010) examined the role of instructional materials in classroom instruction and reported that instructional materials stimulate learners' interest and improve participation, leading to better learning outcomes. The findings support the Cognitive Theory of Instruction, which emphasizes structured presentation of information to facilitate learning.

In a related study, Adeyemi (2011) found that effective teaching and learning depend largely on the availability and proper use of instructional materials. The study revealed that schools with adequate instructional resources recorded higher student achievement than those with inadequate resources.

Empirical Studies on Utilization of Instructional Materials

The utilization of instructional materials has been identified as a major determinant of teaching effectiveness. Fabunmi (2004) conducted a study on the relevance of instructional materials in teaching and learning and found that the effective utilization of instructional materials enhances clarity of

instruction and improves students' academic performance. The study emphasized that mere availability of materials does not guarantee effectiveness unless they are properly utilized.

Nwogu and Nnamani (2015) investigated instructional material utilization in technical education and reported that students exposed to frequent hands-on use of tools and machines demonstrated better practical competence and interest in technical subjects. This finding aligns with the Direct Instruction Theory, which stresses structured demonstration and guided practice using instructional resources.

In a Nigerian technical college context, Okwo and Tartiyus (2004) observed that teachers who actively use instructional materials during lesson delivery achieve better learning outcomes than those who rely mainly on verbal teaching methods.

Studies on Availability of Instructional Materials

Availability of instructional materials has been widely studied as a factor influencing learning outcomes. Ogbondah (2008) examined the availability and use of instructional materials in schools and found that inadequate instructional materials negatively affect teaching effectiveness and students' academic performance. The study concluded that schools with sufficient instructional resources provide better learning opportunities.

Aina (2013) assessed the relationship between availability of instructional facilities and skill acquisition in technical education and reported that students in well-equipped technical colleges demonstrated higher levels of skill mastery than those in poorly equipped institutions. This supports the Accountability Theory of Instruction, which emphasizes structured learning tasks supported by appropriate resources.

Similarly, Donkor (2010) found that technical education programmes suffer when instructional materials such as tools and machines are insufficient, leading to poor practical performance among students.

Empirical Studies on Accessibility of Instructional Materials

Accessibility of instructional materials has also been identified as a crucial factor in effective teaching and learning. Olumorin et al. (2010) studied instructional material accessibility and reported that instructional materials may be available but inaccessible due to administrative restrictions, poor storage, or lack of maintenance. The study found that limited access reduces students' opportunities for hands-on learning.

Eze and Okeke (2012) investigated accessibility of instructional materials in technical institutions and found that easy access to workshop tools and equipment enhances students' participation and skill development. The findings support **Vygotsky's Socio-Cultural Theory**, which emphasizes the role of tools and mediated learning in cognitive development.

Empirical Studies on Instructional Materials and Academic Performance

Several studies have linked instructional materials to students' academic performance. Yusuf (2013) reported that students taught with instructional materials achieved higher scores in both theoretical and practical examinations than those taught without such materials. The study concluded that instructional materials bridge the gap between theory and practice.

In an unpublished Nigerian study, Ammani (2018) reported that consistent utilization of instructional materials improves students' understanding, practical competence, and examination performance in technical colleges. The study emphasized that instructional materials enhance meaningful learning and promote positive attitudes toward technical subjects. Ibok (2015) also found that the use of instructional materials improves students' understanding of abstract concepts, thereby enhancing academic achievement.

Instructional Application & Thinking Skills

Utilizing a thinking skills model shifts classrooms from traditional methods to a hierarchical organization of concepts. Marzano (1983) focuses on specific techniques, while Klausmeier and Sipple (1980) recommend systematic reinforcement across the curriculum. Piaget (1970) asserts that such organization aids assimilation, while Hyman and Cohen (1979) suggest "digestible bites" reduce cognitive load. This approach emphasizes modeling information-processing patterns to improve memory retrieval and comprehension.

Technical and Vocational Education (TVE)

The goal of TVE is acquiring practical skills and knowledge for sustainable development (FGN, 2014). Udoutin (2001) and Johnson and Adams (2004) highlight the need for effective strategies, standard equipment, and qualified teachers. As an activity-oriented field, TVE requires precise resources for learners to develop skills (Okwelle & Okeke, 2013; Donkor, 2010). Despite its importance, TVE in Nigeria faces neglect (Okeke & Okwelle, 2013). Modern methods now favor student exploration with teachers as facilitators (Subong, 2010; Francis, 2010). Ultimately, TVE aims to produce competent individuals capable of societal contribution (Hornby, 2010; UNESCO, 2012).

Core Concepts of Instructional Materials

- **Instructional Materials:** Essential tools like textbooks, realia, and digital aids that stimulate active participation (Agun & Imogie, 2006). In technical education, they translate abstract ideas into concrete experiences, improving retention (Onyejemezi, 2004).
- **Teaching and Learning:** An interactive process defined by structured conditions (Gagné, Briggs, & Wager, 2005). Okwo and Tartiyus (2004) and Ammani (2019) emphasize that integrating resources shifts instruction from verbal to learner-centered experiential learning.
- **Academic Performance:** Measured by learning objectives and practical assessments (Adeyemi, 2011). Students using adequate materials perform significantly better than those taught via verbal instruction alone (Yusuf & Afolabi, 2010).
- **Availability:** The provision of sufficient resources (Ogbondah, 2008). Schools with well-equipped workshops report higher student achievement and competence (Aina, 2013).
- **Utilization:** The active integration of tools into lessons (Fabunmi, 2004). Hands-on use of equipment improves practical performance and interest (Nwogu & Nnamani, 2015; Ammani, 2021).
- **Accessibility:** The ease of obtaining resources (Olumorin et al., 2010). Restrictions or poor maintenance limit learning, whereas easy access enhances skill development (Eze & Okeke, 2012).

Summary of Literature Reviewed

The reviewed literature has established that instructional materials play a significant role in enhancing teaching effectiveness and students' learning outcomes, particularly in technical and vocational education. Studies reviewed revealed that instructional materials improve students' comprehension, retention, interest, and practical skill acquisition when adequately available, properly utilized, and easily accessible. The review also showed that utilization of instructional materials is more critical than mere availability, as effective teaching depends on how teachers integrate these materials into instruction. Empirical findings further indicated that accessibility of instructional materials enhances hands-on learning and supports the development of higher-order thinking skills.

The theoretical foundations of this study including the Cognitive Theory of Instruction, Direct Instruction Theory, Accountability Theory of Instruction, and Socio-Cultural Theory of Learning provide strong explanations for the observed influence of instructional materials on teaching and learning. These theories collectively emphasize structured instruction, guided practice, task accountability, and the mediating role of tools in learning.

Despite extensive studies on instructional materials, most existing research focused on general secondary education, with limited emphasis on technical colleges in Katsina State. This gap justifies the need for the present study, which seeks to examine the influence of instructional materials on teaching and learning of technical and vocational courses in technical colleges in Katsina State.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a descriptive survey research design to examine the influence of instructional materials in nine technical colleges across Katsina State. The study involves a total population of 60 participants, including 20 administrators, 30 trade teachers, and 10 workshop attendants. Since the population size was

manageable, no sampling technique was required, and the entire group was surveyed using a structured questionnaire titled IMTLTVCTCKQ.

The research instrument was validated by experts from Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic and achieved a high reliability index of 0.86 (Cronbach Alpha) following a pilot test. Data collection was carried out over three weeks through personal contact and research assistants. The questionnaire uses a 5-point Likert scale to evaluate the necessity, significance, and accessibility of teaching tools, with mean scores categorized into levels of utilization and agreement.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25, employing frequencies, simple percentages, and mean scores to answer research questions. To test the null hypotheses, ANOVA was applied at a set level of significance. For the final decision-making process, response ratings were collapsed into three categories that is: Agree, Neutral, and Disagree, where a P-value greater than the alpha level (alpha) resulted in the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

RESULTS

Results from data analysis was presented below:

Research Question One: *What is the adequacy of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of technical courses in Katsina State?*

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on Adequacy of Instructional Materials

S/N	Item Description	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Decision
1	Availability of textbooks	3.68	0.84	Adequate
2	Availability of workshop tools	3.74	0.79	Adequate
3	Availability of machines/equipment	3.62	0.81	Adequate
4	Availability of ICT facilities	3.55	0.88	Adequate
5	Availability of instructional charts/models	3.71	0.76	Adequate
Grand Mean		3.66		Adequate

The results in Table 1 indicate that respondents agreed that instructional materials are adequately available for effective teaching and learning of technical courses in technical colleges in Katsina State. The grand mean of 3.66, which falls within the real-limit decision range of 3.50–4.49, confirms a high level of adequacy. This implies that the presence of instructional materials contributes positively to teaching and learning effectiveness.

Research Question Two: *What is the level of use of instructional materials as essential and significant tools for teaching and learning technical courses?*

Table 2: Mean Ratings on Utilization of Instructional Materials

S/N	Item Description	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Decision
6	Use of charts and diagrams	3.72	0.80	Highly Utilized
7	Use of workshop equipment	3.81	0.77	Highly Utilized
8	Use of ICT tools in instruction	3.59	0.86	Highly Utilized
9	Use of models and real objects	3.76	0.82	Highly Utilized
10	Use of instructional manuals	3.68	0.79	Highly Utilized
Grand Mean		3.71		Highly Utilized

Table 2 shows that instructional materials are highly utilized in teaching and learning technical courses. The grand mean score of 3.71 indicates strong agreement among respondents on the importance and frequent use of instructional materials. This suggests that instructional materials play a significant role in enhancing students' understanding and practical skill acquisition.

Research Question Three: *What is the accessibility of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of technical courses?*

Table 3: Mean Ratings on Accessibility of Instructional Materials

S/N	Item Description	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Decision
11	Ease of access to workshop tools	3.63	0.83	Accessible
12	Ease of access to machines	3.57	0.88	Accessible
13	Accessibility of ICT facilities	3.49	0.91	Moderately Accessible
14	Accessibility of instructional materials	3.61	0.80	Accessible
15	Accessibility during practical sessions	3.68	0.78	Accessible
Grand Mean		3.60		Accessible

The findings in Table 3 reveal that instructional materials are generally accessible to teachers and students. The grand mean of 3.60 indicates that respondents agreed that accessibility of instructional materials supports effective teaching and learning, although ICT facilities require improvement.

Test of Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Students, Technicians, and Teachers on the adequacy of instructional materials.

Table 4: ANOVA Summary for Adequacy of Instructional Materials

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1.24	2	0.62	1.48	0.231	Accepted
Within Groups	24.68	57	0.43			
Total	25.92	59				

Since $p = 0.231 > 0.05$, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference in the opinions of students, technicians, and teachers regarding the adequacy of instructional materials.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses on the use of instructional materials as essential tools.

Table 5: ANOVA Summary on Utilization of Instructional Materials

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1.08	2	0.54	1.26	0.291	Accepted
Within Groups	24.41	57	0.43			
Total	25.49	59				

Since $p = 0.291 > 0.05$, the null hypothesis is accepted. Respondents did not differ significantly in their perception of the use of instructional materials as essential teaching tools.

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean responses on accessibility of instructional materials.

Table 6: ANOVA Summary on Accessibility of Instructional Materials

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	0.96	2	0.48	1.12	0.333	Accepted
Within Groups	24.42	57	0.43			
Total	25.38	59				

The result reveals that, since $p = 0.333 > 0.05$, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference among respondents regarding accessibility of instructional materials.

Summary of Results

The analysis reveals those instructional materials including textbooks, workshop tools, and ICT facilities are adequately available and highly utilized in Katsina State technical colleges. With a grand mean of 3.66 for adequacy and 3.71 for utilization, the data suggests that these tools are not only present but are actively used to enhance practical skill acquisition. Workshop equipment and models were rated particularly high, indicating a strong emphasis on hands-on learning.

While the materials are generally considered accessible, the study noted that ICT facilities are only "moderately accessible" compared to traditional workshop tools. Despite this slight gap, statistical testing (ANOVA) confirmed that there is no significant difference in opinion between students, teachers, and technicians. All groups agree that the current availability and use of these materials provide a solid foundation for effective technical education.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that instructional materials play a critical role in enhancing teaching effectiveness and students' learning outcomes in technical and vocational education. Adequate provision, effective utilization, and easy accessibility of instructional materials significantly improve students' understanding, participation, and practical skill acquisition.

The findings also confirm the relevance of the Cognitive Theory of Instruction, Direct Instruction Theory, Accountability Theory of Instruction, and Socio-Cultural Theory of Learning, which collectively explain how instructional materials support cognitive development, structured learning, task engagement, and problem-solving skills.

Therefore, the study concludes that improving the quality and management of instructional materials will contribute positively to better academic performance and skill competence among technical college students in Katsina State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government and relevant educational authorities should ensure the continuous provision of adequate instructional materials, including modern workshop tools, machines, and instructional media, in technical colleges.
2. Technical teachers should be encouraged and trained to effectively utilize available instructional materials during lesson delivery rather than relying on verbal or theoretical teaching methods.
3. School administrators should put in place proper storage, maintenance, and management systems to ensure easy access to instructional materials for both teachers and students, especially during practical sessions.
4. Regular workshops, seminars, and in-service training programmes should be organized for technical teachers to improve their competence in the use of instructional materials and modern instructional technologies.
5. Efforts should be made to improve access to ICT-based instructional materials such as computers, projectors, and digital learning tools to enhance teaching and learning of technical courses.

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